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**EFFECT OF COMPUTER-BASED SIMULATION TEACHING STRATEGY ON SENIOR
SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN BIOLOGY IN ADAMAWA
STATE, NIGERIA**

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ABSTRACT

In view of the importance of Biology in science and technological development, students are expected to have high level of academic achievement in biology both at internal and external examinations. However, Nigerian students face the problem of poor academic achievements in Biology in external examinations. The use of innovative teaching strategies like Computer-Based Simulation (CBS) instructional strategy might help improve this poor learning of Biology. This research is purposely to determine the effects of CBS teaching strategy on learning outcomes in Biology in Adamawa State, Nigeria. The design adopted involves an experimental group taught using CBS and normal instruction served as control. A total of 52,447 students in Adamawa state formed the population of the study. Sample of this study consist of SS 2 Biology students in two intact classes from two schools in Yola education zones in Adamawa state. Data was collected using a validated achievement test instrument. The reliability coefficient of instrument is 0.81. The research questions were answered by descriptive statistics. Whereas the findings of hypothesis were evaluated using ANCOVA statistics. The results revealed a strong effect of CBS in learning Biology. Therefore, CBS is recommended for teaching Biology at secondary school level to help enhance learning of the subject.

Keywords: CBS, Computer-Based Teaching Strategy, Academic Performance, Conventional Teaching Methods

INTRODUCTION

Biology is a branch of science that concern life and living organisms. It involves the systematic study ranging from microscopic cellular molecules to the biosphere, encompassing the earth surface and all living organisms (Ema, 2021). Biology as a natural science is the study of life; their structure, forms, functions, growth, origin, evolutions, distributions, interrelationships, problems such as diseases and adaptation of things (Adewale & Omodoyin, 2020). The subject covers a wide scope comprised of many future careers in science related professions such as agriculture, biotechnology, forestry, medicine, microbiology, nursing and pharmacy and has application nearly in every field of life. Biology plays a significant role and touches almost every aspect of our lives. Biology provides an individual with useful information in solving everyday life challenges. Biology exposes the students to the world of knowledge of one self and his environment. The subject serves as the basis for understanding the complexities of how the body parts of organisms function. According to Nnorom, and Uchegbu (2017), Biology helps learners to understand biological concepts, principles, theories and laws that will enable them face challenges in life before and after graduation.

Biology help students to acquire knowledge and develop understanding of fundamental Biological concepts, terms, principles and facts. Students also understand the applications and uses of Biological knowledge in daily life. Students develop practical techniques and process skills as well as understand current issues and developments in Biology (Abidoeye & Adeyemi, 2023). The Knowledge and practices of Biology have contributed immensely in finding solutions to vital problems in various aspects of life. This includes increasing world food production, development of pesticides for pest control, development of vaccines and drugs for disease control. Other benefits are better health care, hygiene for proper family life as well as plants and animals' hybridization. Studying Biology enable students understand some microorganisms causing global pandemic, management and conservation of natural resources (Udowong, Nneji, & Ighereno, 2023).

Biology occupies a special position in the school curriculum. Ekineh and Adolphus (2019) stated that the subject is popular in Nigeria among students and as a result, has high students' enrolment in external examinations when compared to other science subjects. The objectives of teaching Biology in senior secondary schools as stated in the Nigerian Policy on Education, (FRN, 2013), include the following among others; to train learners understand certain key Biological concepts and acquire adequate laboratory skills on Biology and ability to apply the gained skills in reality. Considering the importance of Biology in science and technological development and to humanity, students are expected to have excel in this subject both at internal and external examinations. However, Nigeria faces the problem of poor students' academic achievements in Biology in external examinations (Adebanjo, 2020).

Novel teaching strategies like CBS instructional strategies is an indispensable as it might help reverse this trend of poor learning of Biology. Thus, this study will focus introduction of CBS instructional strategies in teaching in Adamawa State, Nigeria. Simulation is the creation of real-like (virtual) versions of environments that are natural and real by using computers. Simulation is something that is made to look, feel or behave like something else. Simulation according to Nickson, et al. (2021) is a representation of the behaviour or characteristics of a system by another outlet especially a computer programme designed for a purpose. Simulation has been defined by different authors however, in a broader sense; Simulation means imitation of situation or process, it is a technique that teaches concepts by imitating or replicating the real objects, for example, simulation of blood flowing through arteries or an electron revolving round the outer part of an atom. CBS is an important instructional strategy to depict complex phenomena' especially when the real object is not available or too complex. When any of the instances mentioned above occurs, simulation may turn out to be a better alternative. The inclusion of simulations in education programs has many advantages.

Computer simulations are computer-generated versions of real-world objects. It can be used in the study of dynamic behaviour in an environment that is difficult or dangerous in real life situation. Thus, to eliminate extravagance, possible accidents are prevented, simplifies complexities and moderates learning experiences. Computer simulation are multimedia programmes that comprised of graphics, videos, pictures and other narrations on the computer screen. Computer simulations are emerging technological innovations that are used as instructional media to facilitate understanding of difficult and complex concepts (Simanjuntak, et. al, 2021). Computer simulation facilitates understanding abstract concepts because help students visualize abstract concepts and create mental models of an observed phenomenon due to the integration of new knowledge gathered in the simulation learning environment with the previous ones. Computer simulations instructions help in promoting skill acquisition and retention of students learning experiences. This study is to investigate the effect of Computer-Based simulation teaching on learning outcomes in Adamawa state.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

It is desired that students' academic achievement in secondary schools are comprehensive to qualify for admission in science related courses in the university and other tertiary institution of higher learning. However, the current analysis of students' achievement in Biology revealed that students' academic achievement has remained poor over the years in spite of efforts to improve the learning of Biology at the secondary school level (Biman, Joda, Ugwuadu, & Waziri, 2024). The implication of this persistent poor performance of students in Biology is that a great percentage of the students will not be admitted into higher institutions for Biology related courses, which will lead to the dwindling of man power in Biology and Biology related disciplines. The problem of this study is to investigate the effects of computer-based simulations instructional strategies on senior secondary school students' academic achievement in Biology in Adamawa state, Nigeria.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

This study is to determine the effects of CBS teaching strategy on students' academic performance in Biology in Adamawa State, Nigeria.

RESEARCH QUESTION

The research question that guides this study is:

What are the pre-test and post-test mean achievement scores of students taught Biology with computer-based simulation teaching strategy and those taught with conventional teaching method?

HYPOTHESIS

The following null hypothesis were formulated for the study:

HO₁: There is no significant effect of CBS teaching strategy on students' academic achievement in Biology in Adamawa State.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This section reviewed literature related to CBS on learning outcomes. A study by Niyigena and Nzabalirwa (2022) examined the application of computer simulations to facilitate learning of plants and animal cells. One null hypothesis guided the study. Quasi experimental design was adopted for the study. The study comprised of 240 respondents selected from Musenyi, Nyagihunika and Rulindo schools in Rwanda using purposive sampling technique. The treatment and control groups were taught the same topic of plant and animal cells for two weeks. An experimental group received treatment using cell simulations, while normal classes was treated without simulations. The results proved that using computer simulations improves learners' performance. The reviewed study is related to this study because the studies are similar in instructional strategies, subject, study variable and research design. The studies differ in the study location, level of students and instrument and method of data analysis. The experiment in the reviewed article was conducted at Rwanda, whereas this was conducted in Adamawa, Nigeria.

Okolo and Oluwasegun (2020) studied the effect of CBS on achievement and interest in cell division among male and female students in Abuja, Nigeria. The study was guided by two research questions and two hypotheses. The study adopted quasi-experimental design. The sample of the study consists of 72 (33 males, 39 females) biology students from two intact classes drawn from all the coeducational schools in the six area councils in Abuja. The findings shows that CBS enhanced students learning in learning cell division than the traditional method. The author recommended that CBS should

be used for teaching cell division. The reviewed study is similar to this study in the sense that both studies was on CBS and learning outcomes. The studies are similar in subject, research design and method of data analysis. The studies differ in location and study variables. The reviewed was at Abuja and this study was conducted in Adamawa State. The second dependent variable in the reviewed study is interest while it is retention in this study.

Akhigbe and Ogufere (2020) conducted a research on the effect of CBS strategy on students' learning outcomes in Biology in Lagos, Nigeria. The author used five research questions and five null hypotheses to guide the conduct of the study. Pre-test, post-test, non-randomised, quasi-experimental design with control group was adapted for this study. The sample of the study consists of 209 (127 males, 82 females) biology students drawn from four intact classes using purposive sampling technique in four randomly selected secondary schools in Lagos metropolis. Data were collected using questionnaire and achievement test tagged 'Attitude towards Biology Questionnaire' (ATB) and 'Achievement Test on Genetics' (ATG) respectively with reliability index of 0.78 and 0.84 were respectively. The findings show that CBS as an instructional strategy reasonably improves the achievement and attitude of Biology students. The reviewed study is related to the present study because both studies are similar in terms of teaching strategies, the subject, research design, education level and method of data analysis.

Olumide (2019) carried out a study to determine the effects of CBS and digital puzzle packages on students' learning outcomes (achievement, problem solving skills and attitude) in ecology and genetics in Oyo State, Nigeria. The moderating effects of self-efficacy and mental ability were also examined. A quasi-experimental design by pre-test-post-test control group was adopted. 371 senior secondary two (SS 2) students from eight intact Biology classes randomly selected from eight institutions in Oyo state constitute the study sample. The following instruments were used for data collection; Students' Achievement in Ecology and Genetics ($r=0.80$), Students Problem Solving ($r=0.83$) and Mental Ability ($r =0.85$) tests, Students' Attitude to Ecology and Genetics ($r=0.79$) and Students' Self-efficacy ($r=0.80$). Data was analysed by ANCOVA and Scheffe post-hoc. Participants in computer simulation group had higher achievement mean score, followed by computer simulation and digital puzzle, while the conventional method group had the least adjusted post achievement mean scores. The reviewed study is similar to this study in topic, research design, study subject and method of data analyses. The studies differ in location, study variables and instrument for data collection.

A study by Reddy and Mint (2017) on the impact of simulation based education on biology student's learning at Srinivasa College of education in Thailand. The study was guided by three research questions. Mixed method approach (quantitative and Qualitative) was used. The sample comprises of 70 B.Ed students of the srinivasa College of Education, students that studied B.Ed for first semester 2015/2016 academic session were used for the study. DNA replication biology success test (DRBST) was used as an instrument for data collection, the instrument consists of 30 multiple choice success test questions on DNA replication. The students taught with simulation supported instructions constituted the treatment, whereas conventional teaching constituted the control group. The result revealed that there is an improvement in learning DNA replication using simulation based instruction and the significant improvement is in favour of the female students. In addition, the simulation-supported teaching method in Biology is better than the normal instruction in science education domain.

Similarly, Olalekan and Oludipe (2016) studied the effectiveness of CBS strategy on learning Biology. The study was conducted in Ekiti state, Nigeria. A pre-test-post-test, post-post-test, quasi-experimental design guided the study. The sample size was fifty 300 level undergraduate Biology Education students randomly selected from Ekiti State University (affiliated with Michael Otedola College of Primary Education, Epe). Data was collected by DNA Replication and

Transcription Achievement Test (DRTAT) with 25 multiple-choice questions. The reliability coefficient of 0.70 was established using Kuder-Richardson (KR 20). Data collected was analysed using t-test. The main effect of CBS on means achievement scores of Biology learners is significant also a significant effect on the retention ability of students but no significant effect on gender. Therefore, CBS should be adopted as a means of teaching Undergraduate Biology students in Nigerian university and other tertiary institutions. The two studies are related in the sense that both studied computer simulation on learning outcomes. The two studies were also similar in research design and subject of study. The studies differ in location, level of education and method of data analysis. The previous study was conducted in Ekiti state and this study was conducted in Adamawa state. The previous study was conducted in university while this study was conducted in secondary schools. Furthermore, the reviewed study used t-test for data analysis while this study used ANCOVA.

Iwuanyanwu (2016) studied the effects of simulation game on attitude and performance in Biology in Zaria, Kaduna state. The study was guided by three null hypotheses. The author used quasi-experimental design. The treatment was microorganism instruction using the simulation game strategy, whereas convention teaching control study. The population is all SS1 Biology students of coeducational schools in Zaria education zone, the total population is 2005. One hundred and fifty-three (153) students were selected as sample using multistage sampling technique. Two instruments: Microorganisms Performance Test (MOPT) and Biology Attitude Questionnaire (BAQ) was used for collection of data. Pilot study was conducted and the reliability was calculated using split half method of Gutman. The reliability coefficient of 0.82 and 0.75 was established for the Microorganisms Performance Test (MOPT) and Biology Attitude Questionnaire (BAQ) respectively. The results significantly favoured the students taught microorganisms using simulation game. Furthermore, there was an attitudinal change in the students exposed to simulation game strategy before and after treatment. The author suggested that use of simulation game strategy should be encouraged for Biology instruction at the secondary school level. Seminars and workshops should be organised to train Biology educators on application of simulation game strategy in teaching at the secondary school level.

METHODOLOGY

Quasi-experimental using a pre-test, post-test, non-equivalent, non-randomized, control group was the design of the study. According to Sambo (2008), a study that involves teaching in instructional arrangement is best done through quasi-experimental design. The design was adopted because intact classes was used instead of subjects. Secondary schools classes exist as intact group and any attempt to randomize the subjects may disrupt the school calendar. The experimental groups was exposed to computer-based simulation teaching strategy and traditional method was the control. The research design layout is presented below:

Where

O_1 Represent the pre-test scores for the groups

O_2 Represent the post test scores for the experiment and control groups

X_1 Represent the treatment for experimental group (computer-based simulation teaching

Strategy)

X_C Represent the treatment for Conventional Teaching Method

Population

The population is a total of 52,447 Senior Secondary II Biology students in Adamawa State (Adamawa State Educational Resource Centre, 2022). The justifications for using SS 2 students in this study is because they are stable and are neither new as SS 1 students who were freshly introduced to the subject nor SS 3 students who are facing external examination.

Sample and Sampling Technique

Sample of this study consist of SS 2 Biology students from two schools of same education zones in Adamawa state. Multistage sampling technique was used in selecting the sample. At first stage, cluster sampling technique by lucky dip was used to select one education zones out of the five education zones in the state; Purposive sampling technique was used to select two senior secondary schools from the education zones.

Instrument for Data Collection

A test was used as instrument for data collection. The instrument consists of 50 multiple choice objective tests items with four options (A-D). The instrument was adapted from West African examination Biology past question papers from 2002-2022. The questions was spread according to the Blooms taxonomy of educational objectives. The questions covered the following topics; digestive system, respiratory system, transport system and excretory system.

Validation of the Instrument

The test was selected from past WAEC questions from 2002 to 2022 and therefore considered to be standard. To ensure instruments' the suitability, appropriateness and correctness of the topics covered was subjected to validation by four experts in Biology.

Reliability of the Instrument

After validation, the instrument was pilot tested to 30 SS 2 Biology students at Government Day Senior Secondary School (GSS), Girei, a school with similar educational background and offering Biology but not part of the study area. Kuder-Richardson KR-21 formula was used and 0.81 was obtained as the coefficient, which means the instrument is reliable.

Procedure for Data Collection

Data was collected using an aptitude test. Two experienced Biology teachers, one from each school served as research assistants. The research assistants was trained for one week on how to teach using the teaching strategies specified for each group by the already designed lesson plans for each group. Lesson plans and materials were given to the research assistants after the training. The experimental group 1 was taught using computer-based simulation, whereas the control groups by normal instruction. The exercise lasted for seven weeks. In the first week, a pre-test was conducted to all groups to ascertain their entry behaviour and the script was collected, marked and scored. Subsequently, treatments was conducted, which lasted for five weeks. After the treatments, post-test was administered in the sixth week to all the groups using the same instrument (BAT) but the items was reshuffled so that it cannot be easily recognised by the students, the script collected was marked and recorded. Total correct answers scored 100 marks.

Method of Data Analysis

The data collected was analysed using descriptive and inferential statistical. Descriptive statistics was used to answering research question and inferential statistics was ANCOVA for hypothesis. The alpha level of 0.05 was used as the

acceptable significance level for rejecting or upholding all the hypotheses. The decision rule for hypothesis testing is that if $p < 0.05$, then the effect is significant on the variables, but if $p > 0.05$ then it is not significant on the variables.

RESULTS

This section presents the results obtained in answering research question and hypothesis testing.

Answering Research Questions

What are the pre-test and post-test mean achievement scores of students taught Biology with computer-based simulation teaching strategy and those taught with conventional teaching method?

Table 1: Pre-test and Post-test Mean Performance Scores of CBS and CTM

GROUP		PRETEST	POSTTEST	MEAN GAIN
CONTROL	N	58	58	
	Mean	30.50	55.24	24.74
	Std. Deviation	7.047	9.797	
EXPRMT	N	84	84	
	Mean	31.14	63.26	32.12
	Std. Deviation	5.469	13.397	
Total	N	142	142	
	Mean	30.88	59.99	
	Std. Deviation	6.147	12.653	

Analysis in Table 1 displayed the pre – test and post – test mean performance scores of Biology students taught by CBS teaching strategy and those by CTM method. The pre – test and post – test mean performance by CBS teaching strategy are $\bar{x} = 31.14$, $S.D = 5.469$ and $\bar{x} = 63.26$, $S.D = 13.397$ respectively. The result also reveals that the pre – test and post – test mean performance scores by CTM are $\bar{x} = 30.50$, $S.D = 7.047$ and $\bar{x} = 63.26$, $S.D = 13.397$ respectively. The mean gain between the pre – test and post – test performance scores of the students in the CBS group and CTM group are 32.12 and 24.74 respectively with CBS group recorded higher.

Result of Hypotheses Testing

HO₁: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught Biology with CBS teaching strategy and those taught with conventional teaching method.

Table 2: Summary of ANCOVA of Difference Between the Performances of Students taught Biology using CBS and CTM Teaching Methods.

Dependent Variable: POSTTEST

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	2342.740 ^a	2	1171.370	8.048	.000	.104
Intercept	15859.998	1	15859.998	108.967	.000	.439
PRETEST	135.627	1	135.627	.932	.336	.007
GROUP	2145.220	1	2145.220	14.739	.000	.096
Error	20231.232	139	145.548			
Total	533534.000	142				
Corrected Total	22573.972	141				

a. R Squared = .104

Analysis in Table 2 presented summary of ANCOVA conducted to test whether the effect of CBS teaching strategy is significantly higher than the CTM. The result obtained revealed that $F(1, 141) = 14.739, p < 0.000$ with large effect size as indicated by the partial Eta squared of 0.096. Since the significant value of 0.000 obtained was < 0.05 , as such the author rejected the hypothesis. Thus, it means that the improvement in students' academic achievement when taught Biology using CBS teaching strategy over those taught with CTM is significant.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This study shows that the achievement recorded by students in the CBS teaching strategy superseded the CTM group. This implies that CBS teaching strategy, which involves creation of virtual environments for real Biology concepts by using computer systems is an effective instructional strategy. This strategy helps students learn the Biology better than the normal teaching methods. This result aligns with the studies conducted by Niyigena and Nzabalarwa (2022), Okolo and Oluwasegun (2020) and Olumide (2019) that CBS as an efficient instructional tool that significantly improves students' academic performance.

CONCLUSION

It can be concluded from the outcome of this that CBS as a strategy can improve learning Biology compared to conventional teaching methods. This study discovered that instruction using CBS showed higher students' performance compared to instruction using conventional teaching methods. These findings confirmed the novelty of CBS in improving Biology education.

RECOMMENDATION

The authors recommend that Biology educators and educational leadership use CBS to help enhance students' performance, understanding and engagement in the subject.

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